

Towards Sustainable Mobility: A Roadmap for establishing a Community of Practice in Porto

María Alonso Raposo • Juliana Carvalho •
Máté János Lőrincz • Emma Lawlor • Rebecca Rossetti

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KNOWLEDGE BROKERAGE INITIATIVE DEVELOPED BY

María Alonso
Raposo
cambiaMO |
changing MObility

Juliana Carvalho
University of Porto
- INESC TEC

Máté János
Lőrincz
University of
Reading

Emma Lawlor
University of
Glasgow

Rebecca Rossetti
University of
Bologna

Supported by Julius Wesche, The Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) (mentor)

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1. Introduction

SSH CENTRE (*Social Sciences and Humanities for Climate, Energy aNd Transport Research Excellence*) is a project funded by the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The project aims to support cross-sectoral collaboration and empower citizens and networks to develop socially innovative solutions for the European Union's (EU) climate transition, as well as strengthening SSH-STEM collaboration, transdisciplinary policy advice, inclusive engagement and SSH communities across Europe¹. More information on the project is available [via its website](https://sshcentre.eu).

In 2023, the project launched its Knowledge Brokerage Programme on Sustainability Transitions which aims to design and implement Knowledge Brokerage (KB) activities for climate, energy and mobility policy-making. The Programme involves 30 early- and mid-career researchers with a Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) background, organised into six teams, each of which is developing an SSH KB initiative in cooperation with a European city administration.

This is the Communities of Practice (CoP) Document of the Mobility Communities KB initiative in Porto, Portugal. The initiative is developed in partnership with the Municipality of Porto. Participants in this work: Daniel Freitas, Head of Carbon Neutrality in Porto; André Brochado, Mayor's Advisor; Ana Sofia Barreto, Head of the Municipal Mobility Department; Bruno Eugénio, Head of the Municipal Division of Mobility Management; and José Ferreira, Municipal Division of Mobility Planning. The research team consists of: María Alonso Raposo, cambiaMO; Juliana Carvalho, University of Porto - INESC TEC; Máté János Lőrincz, University of Reading; Emma Lawlor, University of Glasgow; and Rebecca Rossetti, University of Bologna. The research team is supported by Julius Wesche, on behalf of the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), which is an SSH CENTRE consortium partner.

The main aim of this KB initiative is to provide SSH perspectives and methods to help identify the mobility-related challenges faced by the city of Porto and potential strategies leading to improved sustainable urban mobility in line with its strong climate ambitions. The core purpose is to kickstart the formation of a collaborative network where various stakeholders related to mobility in Porto can actively engage in sharing knowledge and forming a CoP. Following the sign-off of the plan (defined in the "design document"), the main initiative lasted 6 months (February to July 2024). An intermediate workshop (City Hub Workshop) was held on the 17th and 18th of April in Porto.

In particular, this CoP report explores the purpose and importance of CoPs, particularly in promoting sustainable mobility practices. Drawing on key findings from the mobility literature, it is explored how CoPs facilitate knowledge sharing and collaboration between different stakeholders. Best practices for analysing mobility data from multiple sources within a CoP setting are also highlighted. Ultimately, this report provides the knowledge and practical guidance needed to establish and manage an effective CoP dedicated to advancing sustainable mobility solutions.

Section two of this document is focused on establishing and running a CoP. It begins by exploring the conceptual aspects of CoPs, reflecting on their significance in knowledge management, particularly in fostering learning, innovation, and problem-solving. Next, the focus is on potential topics that can be addressed through CoPs, outlining different types and their applicability. Attention is then given to identifying key stakeholders, detailing their roles and responsibilities, and highlighting the importance of diverse participation and expertise. Subsequently, the steps necessary for initiating CoPs are explained, strategies for fostering participation and engagement, best practices for sustaining CoPs over time, and addressing challenges with potential solutions for effective management. Following this, real-world case study examples of successful CoPs in various fields are presented, illustrating how they were established, operated, and maintained, along with the lessons learned and insights gained from each case study. The section concludes with key findings from the report and outlines the next steps for the KB initiative.

Section three focuses on presenting a preliminary roadmap for establishing a CoP in Porto, Portugal. Based on foundational activities and insights from a recent workshop in the city, a preliminary roadmap for establishing a CoP in Porto is outlined. This roadmap is designed to serve as a starting point for creating a CoP focused on sustainable urban mobility, fostering ongoing

¹ More information on the project is available here: <https://sshcentre.eu>

collaboration and engagement. It begins with an overview of Porto's urban mobility challenges and sustainability goals, followed by key mobility issues that underscore the strategic importance of a CoP. Insights from the workshop are provided, highlighting the role of data in sustainable urban mobility transitions. The section concludes by addressing the next steps for establishing a CoP in Porto, revisiting the core questions of why, what, who, and how to create and manage a CoP for sustainable urban mobility.

Section four is focused on drawing conclusions from our exploration of CoPs and their application in sustainable urban mobility, particularly within the context of Porto. This section highlights some key aspects to consider, such as including stakeholder engagement, capacity building, policy advocacy, implementation of sustainable mobility projects, and establishing robust monitoring and evaluation processes.

2. Establishing and running a Community of Practice

This section aims to clarify the Community of Practice (CoP) concept and activities, by answering four key questions:

1. **Why do Communities of Practice matter?** Definition of CoPs and their significance in knowledge management.
2. **What aspects are addressed through Communities of Practice?** Example case studies of CoP in the mobility field.
3. **Who participates in Communities of Practice?** Mapping key stakeholders and roles, highlighting the importance of ensuring a diverse CoP based on the Quadruple Helix.
4. **How to establish and sustain Communities of Practice?** Including initiating a CoP, benefits and limits of stakeholders engagement and participation.

2.1. Why do Communities of Practice matter?

Communities of practice (CoPs) are groups of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly (Wenger, McDermott and Snyder, 2002). CoPs connect people with common interests and goals to enhance knowledge and support action in a given field of expertise. In the mobility context, CoPs have been organised to enact processes of learning with the engagement of actors from the mobility ecosystem (e.g. citizens, policy-makers, operators and developers of new mobility services). For example, local CoPs organised in five European and Western Asian countries have helped gain insights about the needs of target users of different digital mobility solutions, develop common knowledge about their potential adoption and create a common space for their co-design to make them more inclusive (Di Ciommo et al. 2023). Overall, participation in CoPs may contribute to improving current practices in a given field (Wynn et al., 2023).

CoPs support the transmission and expansion of knowledge and expertise, and enhance collaboration and connectedness. Knowledge is often equated with know-how, experience, insight, understanding and contextualised information. According to Gamble et al. (2001), “*knowledge is a fluid mix of framed experience, values, contextual information, expert insight and grounded intuition that provides an environment and framework for evaluating and incorporating new experiences and information*”. The underlying idea is that knowledge is not an object that is stored and transferred, nor an already constructed idea of the world that is transmitted from an instructor to a learner. Instead, knowledge is built through social interactions. In this way, CoPs represent creative spaces for researching, generating and sharing practice-oriented knowledge to jointly build new ideas and behaviours. Knowledge management results from the interaction of three constituent elements of a CoP: domain, community and practice (Wenger 2004). Knowledge management can thus be seen as a cyclical and strategic activity that enables members of CoPs to share experiences and develop expertise essential to their work. Through ongoing interaction, CoP participants can share their insights collaboratively, fostering a culture of mutual learning and continuous improvement within their specific field.

The European Commission’s ‘Science4Policy’ Competence Framework identifies CoPs and networks as cornerstones for knowledge sharing and collective intelligence (see B6 competence

in [Competence Framework ‘Science for Policy’ for researchers | Knowledge for policy \(europa.eu\)](#)). They are essential to increase the impact of science in policy making, ensuring that the most useful and robust evidence is provided and understood in time to be considered by policy-makers throughout the policy cycle. It responds to the needs stated in the communication “Data, Information and Knowledge Management at the European Commission” (European Commission 2016). In this document it is highlighted that creating thematic CoP, professional networks and exchange of best practices could contribute to achieving the key policy priorities. In this context, the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre (JRC) examined the life cycle of communities of practice in the European Commission and developed ‘The Communities of Practice Playbook’ (European Commission et al., 2021). It provides practical guidance, interactive tools and best practices to empower community managers and stakeholders, and foster vibrant and effective CoPs. The playbook serves as a roadmap for creating, nurturing and sustaining communities that facilitate collective learning, innovation and problem solving in diverse organisational contexts.

Based on Di Ciommo et al., (2021), CoPs:

- Serve as arenas for exploring, generating and disseminating practical knowledge among CoP participants.
- Enable members to express a common concern or enthusiasm about their work and to acquire skills in addressing it through interaction with peers.
- Encourage knowledge creation through peer-to-peer learning within the group, drawing on the expertise and experience of its members while incorporating external insights.
- Use the expertise and experience of its members to develop solutions tailored to their needs and interests, empowering CoP participants through peer-to-peer learning.
- May have different objectives, such as developing efficient services, cultivating shared knowledge or enhancing specific group capabilities.
- Can be organised as virtual meetings, face-to-face meetings or a mixture of virtual and face-to-face formats.
- Facilitate the development of shared perspectives through group dynamics, discussions and collaborative exercises such as simulations.
- Provide appropriate platforms for sharing experiences across different geographical and cultural contexts.
- Are structured and facilitated (as opposed to spontaneous gatherings) to ensure productive outcomes and knowledge creation.
- Establish specific agendas for each CoP meeting with a clear thematic focus and document the proceedings in the form of minutes.
- Encourage and facilitate dialogue with subject matter experts who can bring valuable insights to the discussions.

In sum, CoPs are vital for sharing practical knowledge, fostering skill development among peers and solving real-world challenges collaboratively. They bring people together to learn, exchange ideas and address common concerns, whether through virtual or in-person meetings. CoPs provide structured platforms for discussion, to improve current practices in a given field.

² More information can be found here:

https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/visualisation/competence-framework-%E2%80%98science-policy%E2%80%99-researchers_en

2.2. What aspects are addressed through CoPs?

The starting point in the establishment of a CoP should be the definition of the purpose or mission of the community (i.e. why does the community exist?) together with the co-creation of a shared vision (i.e. where the community is going?). The long-term shared vision inspires people to contribute and collaborate for the success of the community. These elements set the scope of a community and help identify which aspects need to be addressed during the life cycle of a community, which are often translated into a set of specific, measurable, achievable, realistic and timely (SMART) objectives.

In the context of sustainable urban mobility transitions, establishing a CoP can be a strategic move to ensure a more comprehensive and creative approach.

CoPs are increasingly being used to improve knowledge sharing and collaboration in multiple fields of practice. Tables 1 to 5 present some relevant real-world examples of CoPs in various fields, showcasing the growing emphasis to improve knowledge sharing and collaboration.

Table 1. Knowledge Sharing for Better Implementation of EU regional policy (KNOW SHARE) project

Knowledge Sharing for Better Implementation of EU regional policy (KNOW SHARE) project, 2015-2017 (Source: https://policy-lab.ec.europa.eu/news/co-designing-bottom-community-improve-management-european-regional-development-funds-regio-knowshare-2016-06-22_en)
<p>An example of a successful knowledge sharing, collaboration and learning case comes from the project “Knowledge Sharing for Better Implementation of EU regional policy – KNOW SHARE” (Svanfeldt et al., 2016). It proposes innovative approaches and principles enabling the creation of bottom-up CoPs among national and regional administrations in charge of the management of European structural and investment funds. A key output of the KNOW SHARE project is a report entitled “Enabling Communities of Practice”. The report provides a co-designed proposal to enable the creation of bottom-up CoP among national and regional administrations responsible for the management of European Structural and Investment Funds.</p> <p>LESSONS LEARNED: This project suggests that major benefits could be generated by enabling a horizontal exchange mechanism driven by actual “users”, such as increased quality and efficiency of implementation of European Funds. Creating a CoP for knowledge exchange can go beyond regional and cohesion policy, which makes this work of wider interest and potentially of great relevance to other policy initiatives aimed at promoting knowledge sharing, cooperation and learning.</p>

Table 2. Inclusive Digital Mobility Solutions (INDIMO) project

Inclusive Digital Mobility Solutions (INDIMO) project (Horizon 2020 project), 2020-2022 (Source: https://www.indimoproject.eu/)
<p>In the INDIMO project, CoPs were established at five pilot locations: Monghidoro (Italy), Antwerp (Belgium), Galilée (Israel), Madrid (Spain) and Berlin (Germany) (Di Ciommo et al., 2023). In each pilot, CoPs included users, mobility service providers, (digital) developers, user interface designers and policymakers associated. Purposes varied across pilots and thus addressed specific mobility solutions, namely: digital lockers, inclusive traffic lights, informal ride-sharing in multi-ethnic towns, a cycle logistics platform for healthy food delivery and on-demand ride-sharing integrated into multimodal route planning.</p> <p>LESSONS LEARNED: CoPs created a safe space, allowing people from different disciplines and practice areas to come together and share information. This enhanced the collaboration among different actors who oversee different features of digital mobility and delivery solutions (i.e., digital, physical and regulatory features) and was crucial to build up common knowledge and empower the participants, including the target groups of vulnerable users. For this to be achieved, CoP facilitators need to be trained beforehand on how to set up and run a CoP which includes acquiring communication and listening skills beyond the technical skills related to the solutions under study.</p>

Table 3. Developing Business-to-Business (B2B) electric car sharing as a sustainable mode of work travels: a community-based affordances perspective

Developing B2B electric car sharing as a sustainable mode of work travels: a community-based affordances perspective, 2023
<p>In a recent example (Julstrup et al., 2023), the uptake of shared electric cars (SEC) in two communities of mobile workers in Norway was analysed based on a combination of CoP and affordances theories. The term community-based affordance describes how new mobility technologies are enacted and made sense of in the community, leading to transformations in work and mobility practices. Five community-based affordances are identified for the SEC-system: replacements of private cars, customised use of vehicles, rapid reimbursement, co-riding to meetings and commuting mode reconfigurations. Together, these affordances indicate how an SEC- system can contribute to the development of sustainable mobility practices in enterprises with many mobile workers.</p> <p>LESSONS LEARNED: Julstrup et al., (2023) proposes a framework that emphasises the social dimension of technological innovations, applying the concept of CoP that addresses technologies as ‘social objects’ involved in the development of shared knowledge, meaning and identity. The authors combined a social practice and an affordances perspective, through the term ‘community-based affordances’, to study how SECs are utilised by a community of practitioners and the emerging affordances they evoke. This work has helped to identify key areas where such technologies can lead to changes in working practices and travel behaviour, delivering benefits for environmental sustainability as well as internal communications and workflows.</p>

Table 4. The role of communities of practice in improving practice in Indigenous health and education settings: A systematic review

The role of communities of practice in improving practice in Indigenous health and education settings: A systematic review, 2023
<p>This paper (Wynn et al. 2023) reviews the role of CoP in improving practice of existing workforce development strategies in Indigenous health and education settings. Seven databases were searched up to 2020. Eleven qualitative studies were included and data synthesised using thematic analysis.</p> <p>LESSONS LEARNED: Most of the included studies focused on CoP in education settings and included both Indigenous and non-Indigenous health and education professionals. CoPs allowed them to share stories, knowledge and resources and supported them to develop culturally responsive tools, assessments and strategies. This may improve Indigenous health and education outcomes. Participation in CoP coupled with increased training and teaching about Indigenous culture may play a role in improving the practice of Indigenous health and education professionals.</p>

Table 5. REthinking and FOstering Competence and skills for sUustainable transport, Shipping and logistics (REFOCUS) project (ERASMUS + project) lessons learned

REthinking and FOstering Competence and skills for sUustainable transport, Shipping and logistics (REFOCUS) project (ERASMUS + project), 2023-2025 (on-going) (Source: https://refocus-project.eu/)
<p>REFOCUS has used CoPs to engage academia (learners and educators), companies and organisations (labour market) in an interactive co-design process to create future-oriented curriculum and training material on sustainability and climate resilience for transport, shipping and logistics sectors. CoPs were organised in 4 European countries: Spain, Belgium, Greece and The Netherlands. They helped identify the knowledge needs in the transport, shipping and logistics sectors from an educational point of view.</p> <p>LESSONS LEARNED: All the CoPs sessions were organised online, which presented challenges in sustaining engagement and participation, building relationships without face-to-face interactions, ensuring technology reliability, navigating cultural and time zone differences and facilitating effective leadership and collaboration in a virtual environment. These challenges require careful consideration and proactive strategies to create inclusive, productive and sustainable online CoP.</p>

These examples show how CoP can be used in different ways and what can be learned from them. Communities can contribute to more comprehensive, innovative, and effective Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMPs). SUMPS are a European success story involving cities, citizens and strong European policy coordination and support. They are based on practical guidelines developed through consultation with practitioners and an active CoP (Wefering et al., 2013).

2.3. Who participates in a Community of Practice?

After establishing the main purpose and vision of the CoP, it is important to establish who should be involved and how. These are the stakeholders who need and want to get involved and/or those who are impacted by the CoP. A stakeholder map is a suitable tool to support this identification, as it enables a visual representation of the various stakeholders and their relationships within the CoP. By creating a stakeholder map, key players can be identified, their level of influence or interest assessed, and determination of the best ways to engage with them. This strategic approach can help ensure that the CoP is well-supported and that the right people are involved in achieving its goals.

According to the European Commission report, 'The Communities of Practice Playbook', stakeholder mapping can be defined as "...the (visual) process of identifying and laying out all the stakeholders of your community. This is usually a visual representation of all the people who have an interest in the community, who can influence it, and/or are likely to be affected by it. The mapping also shows how these people relate to the community." (European Commission et al., 2021).

To facilitate this process, the quadruple helix framework can be utilised as a tool to map out the sectors from which stakeholders will be invited to participate in the CoP. The framework emphasises four key areas: government, industry, academia, and civil society. By identifying specific actors within each of these areas, a comprehensive and diverse stakeholder map can be developed. This approach not only ensures broad representation and inclusion but also promotes innovation, knowledge sharing, and sustainable development within the community. Figure 1 displays an example of how to use this framework, placing a potential key objective at the centre of the framework and exploring what actors might be relevant in this context.

Figure 1. The quadruple helix

Source: Adapted from Schütz et al., 2019), STEM = Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics; A = Arts; SSH= Social Sciences and Humanities

Identifying and involving stakeholders who possess the necessary skills and knowledge for effective planning and implementation within a CoP is essential. This ensures a comprehensive approach where key functional abilities are present, including:

- Capacity to gain political support
- Competence over relevant networks and services
- Technical excellence in development
- Capacity to gain public support or understand the urgencies and needs of the public

To ensure a democratic and inclusive approach, it is important to map stakeholders and assess their level of interest and power in relation to the community of practice. This can be achieved using a stakeholder matrix or power-interest grid, which categorises stakeholders based on their influence and interest in the community’s initiatives (or influence-interest matrix, as shown in Figure 2). By plotting stakeholders on this grid, it can identify those who need to be closely managed, those who should be kept informed, those who require regular monitoring, and those who need to be kept satisfied.

Figure 2. The influence-interest matrix

Source: adapted based on Wefering et al., 2013

This categorisation helps to ensure that all relevant voices are included, especially those from underrepresented groups. By evaluating stakeholders' influence and engagement, strategies can be developed to empower marginalised groups, ensuring their meaningful participation. This inclusive approach fosters equity, builds trust, and enhances the overall effectiveness and sustainability of the community of practice, ultimately contributing to sustainable urban mobility.

When mapping stakeholders, it is important to be mindful of the objective of their involvement. This can be achieved in several ways (Patuelli et al., 2021; Tellioglu et al., 2013):

- **Nominal participation** enables legitimation and inclusion from other points of view. In this case, a governmental institution or organisation sponsors the participation activity, allowing the inclusion of stakeholders in the participatory group.
- **Instrumental participation** is intended as a participatory activity that provides labour for essential services for the sponsor organisation or government, and stakeholders' involvement is a cost in terms of time and resources.
- **Representative participation** is not direct participation of all stakeholders, but participation is handled by the sponsoring organisation or governmental body over the long term.
- **Transformative participation** is the bottom-up process, where stakeholder empowerment is desired.

All these approaches can be effective in mobility planning but the one closest to the aim of building a CoP is the transformative participation. To make this bottom-up process possible, it is important to start considering the different backgrounds and individual characteristics of each stakeholder to facilitate a heterogeneous group that is as inclusive as possible (based on the possible stakeholder types identified in Table 6).

Table 6. Key stakeholders for a Community of Practice in the mobility field

Stakeholders	Roles and responsibilities
Transport planners and engineers	Professionals involved in urban transport planning, design and engineering who are responsible for developing and implementing strategies to improve mobility, accessibility and safety in cities.
Policy-makers and government officials	Decision-makers and policy-makers at local, regional and national levels responsible for shaping urban transport policies, regulations and investments to address mobility challenges and promote sustainable transport solutions.
Transport operators and service providers	Representatives from public transport operators, private transport companies and mobility service providers involved in the operation and management of transport services such as buses, trains, ridesharing and micro-mobility options.
Community advocates and activists	Representatives of community-based organisations, advocacy groups and grassroots movements working for equitable access to transport, affordable housing and sustainable urban development.
Academics and researchers	Academics, researchers and educators from universities and research institutions conducting studies and research on urban transport, mobility behaviour and sustainable urban development.
Business and industry representatives	Representatives from the business sector, including transport-related industries, technology companies and start-ups, who provide expertise, resources and investment to support innovation and entrepreneurship in urban mobility.
Citizens	Individuals of all ages, genders, orientations, beliefs and political views. The term means someone who lives in a particular place, (i.e. a village, town, city, region, state, or country).

Maintaining a diverse mix of participants and expertise within CoPs is crucial to foster innovation and creative problem solving. This diversity ensures a broader understanding of complex urban mobility challenges by including a wider range of viewpoints and approaches. In addition, diverse participation promotes inclusivity and equity, ensuring that underrepresented voices are heard and valued, ultimately leading to more equitable solutions. By drawing on a wider pool of expertise and experience, CoPs can develop more robust, contextually relevant solutions that effectively address the mobility challenges faced by cities. Through greater representativeness and inclusiveness, CoPs can potentially contribute to wider public acceptability of the proposed solutions.

With regard to the possible roles and responsibilities within a CoP, the following key roles should be considered:

- **Facilitators or moderators:** individuals responsible for facilitating discussions, organising CoP meetings and promoting collaboration within the CoP, ensuring that meetings are productive and inclusive.
- **CoP members:** diverse public and private stakeholders and wider society. Members act as knowledge brokers or intermediaries between research, practice and policy. Some may become community champions (i.e. individuals who actively advocate for sustainable transport solutions, mobilise support and engage stakeholders).
- **Funding actors or sponsors:** organisations that provide financial support, resources or grants to sustain and promote the activities of the CoP.

This section has reviewed the possible stakeholders to engage in a CoP, discussing their influence, interest, roles and responsibilities. Mapping stakeholders contributes to defining the membership of the CoP and the surrounding community ecosystem, and should be a step towards defining the governance of the community in terms of how members work together and make decisions.

2.4. How to establish and sustain Communities of Practice?

The Communities of Practice Playbook states that “*the more a community creates something concrete together, the more engaged it is*” (European Commission, 2021). This requires the co-creation of tangible assets/deliverables resulting from effective coordination of different cooperation and collaboration processes. Whereas cooperation occurs from the individual rather than collective effort through the exchange of relevant knowledge in support of each other’s goals, collaboration means working together to create a shared outcome in support of a shared vision, shared goals or a shared purpose. The challenge is to devise and implement a sustained action plan that will yield results, including the activities and resources required to help the community achieve value. This should include support for continuous communications and updates, a timeline, task and project management, and a user-centric experience.

CoPs typically go through several stages of development (Figure 3):

1. **Committing:** Initiated by one or more stakeholder who recognise the value of collaboration and decide to convene a CoP.
2. **Starting up:** Goals are set, stakeholders are recruited and roles within the CoP begin to take shape.
3. **Operating:** Involves knowledge sharing, problem solving, skill building and sharing of everyday practices, often characterised by high levels of engagement and tangible impacts on practitioners’ activities.
4. **Winding down:** As the CoP achieves its goals and addresses key challenges, engagement may wane, signalling a natural decline in the value of the organisation.

5. **Shutting down:** Whether due to the achievement of its goals or the resolution of its focus areas, the CoP reaches a point of closure. Practitioners are given advance notice of the CoP's impending closure, allowing for reflection on its legacy and expressions of gratitude to all participants.

Figure 3. Lifecycle of a CoP (Source: Wenger et al., 2002)

2.4.1. Committing: Initiating a Community of Practice with a knowledge base

Building a CoP requires following many steps that highlight the importance of the values and needs behind the community, the policies already in place and their possible extension, and the participation of stakeholders in the policymaking process. Knowledge brokering is part of these fundamental steps in terms of providing research findings to policymakers in a way that can challenge the traditional policymaking process.

The building process for a CoP can start with a **Quantitative stage**. It refers to the preliminary steps that are necessary to establish the basis for an effective CoP. This is the knowledge base that helps understand the context and problem being addressed. It includes a literature review on the topic selected. In addition, it may be beneficial to conduct interviews with a group of people that can be potentially involved. These interviews are needed if there is not enough available data on citizens' perceptions and needs on the problem being addressed. This phase serves as evidence to substantiate results. The additional quantitative steps relate to knowledge management to inform the stakeholders and define possible scenarios.

2.4.2. Starting up and operating: Engagement strategies

Building a CoP requires a **Participatory stage**. It is based on collaboration and co-creation as well as capacity building and requires the engagement of stakeholders in different ways. Using effective participatory approaches is crucial from the beginning to the end of a CoP. For example, from the co-creation of a shared vision and objectives to the co-creation and implementation of possible solutions. A co-creation approach always involves understanding the needs of different stakeholders. At this stage, it is also possible to study users' experiences, including what they think, do and feel. A broad base of people can actively advocate for change and make efforts to reach individualised common objectives. Participation in co-creation is critical and needs to be incentivised through practices and tools. There are a variety of effective and feasible engagement methods which could be used.

Stakeholders are identified and invited to join a CoP to achieve a shared vision and objectives. They are often not automatically involved in the process unless engagement strategies are applied. The objective of the engagement process is to recognise the stakeholders who decide to collaborate in a CoP as legitimate participants in science for policy. Stakeholders, including citizens, are knowledge-holders and able to enrich the research with new and diverse perspectives. However, their engagement is not always autonomous, and it needs to be encouraged. To foster participation, individuals involved in a CoP should plan and design engagement strategies and anticipate the purpose of those. During the formation phase, scope and objectives are defined and drive the criteria for recruiting new participants according to these objectives.

Engagement plays a key role at the operation phase, where the knowledge sharing is implemented, extended and policy issues are assessed. Different types of engagement strategies are relevant for different stages. The engagement process is open to diversity of views and values, creating bridges between different stakeholders through co-facilitated conversations, synthesised inputs, reports as well as debates and disagreements, managed with specific techniques. Indeed, the process of engagement values the active listening to others, toleration and interactions that need to be clear and effectively use verbal and non-verbal communication.

Examples of engagement methods include storytelling workshops, *personas* and scenario-building, future backcasting, world cafés, and serious games. For example, in the context of CoPs and mobility, storytelling could help in creating collaboration across disciplines and sectors by helping visualise the transition to a more sustainable mobility. Also, serious gaming could be used to prioritise learning for change based on gaming principles, going beyond mere entertainment and raising awareness and understanding of complex issues. Each of these methods has distinct purposes and advantages but also face different challenges, therefore choosing the right method according to the specific objectives is essential. Further, it is important to plan and organise when formal and informal convening opportunities should take place.

2.4.3. Winding down and shutting down: Monitoring the progress and outcomes of a CoP

Monitoring the performance of a CoP is an ongoing process, rather than a one-off annual exercise. It is the responsibility of the community manager (understood as the person or team in charge of coordinating the activities of the CoP, following the propositions presented in European Commission et al., 2021) to continuously monitor the community's health by using quantitative and qualitative indicators (such as number and type of participants, feedback from CoP members) that help assess the results, engagement, and vitality of the CoP. The goal is to ensure that the community remains relevant and engaged (i.e. there is value in being part of it), and that it delivers on its vision.

The value of membership decreases as the problems the CoP set out to address are solved and practice improves. Once the purpose is fulfilled, there is little/no value left and the decision is made to shut down. Upon closure, the final outcomes and materials of the CoP are shared. Also, reflections and lessons learned are collected, such as through a final meeting, workshop or survey, to take into consideration for the establishment of future CoPs.

3. Roadmap for establishing a CoP: Lessons from the Porto Workshop

In this section, a brief roadmap for establishing a Community of Practice (CoP) in Porto, Portugal is presented. This roadmap was developed using several foundational activities and insights gathered from a workshop in the city (April 2024). This roadmap serves as an initial framework to guide the establishment of a CoP in sustainable urban mobility for Porto. It is intended as a starting point for ongoing collaboration and enhancement, providing a foundation for future steps. The broad framing acknowledges that a more comprehensive understanding of mobility needs and aspirations is essential to effectively promote public transport uptake while reducing the use of private cars. This approach aims to contribute to improved quality of life and decarbonisation efforts.

In the following subsection, an overview of the city of Porto is presented, with special attention to urban mobility issues and the sustainability commitments and ambitions of the municipality. Next, there is a focus on key mobility issues that help to understand why a CoP could be a strategic participatory and collaborative mechanism to support the city in its urban mobility transition. Following on, key information about the workshop and some insights about the centrality of data to address sustainable urban mobility transitions are reported.

The overall goal of the CoP is to create a better understanding of the motivations, needs and aspirations of citizens and key urban mobility players, enabling the city to more effectively promote public transport and active mobility whilst also reducing the usage of private vehicles. Using this goal, the following section addresses the next steps to establish a CoP for the city of Porto, revising the key questions addressed in the previous overview of why, what, who and how to establish and run a CoP in the context of sustainable urban mobility transitions.

3.1. Porto: A city committed to carbon neutrality and sustainable mobility

Porto is a municipality located in the northern region of Portugal and is one of the 17 municipalities that form the Metropolitan Area of Porto, the second largest urban area of Portugal, after Lisbon. The city has a population of approximately 231,800 inhabitants, whilst the metropolitan area reaches a total of 1,736,228 inhabitants (Instituto Nacional de Estatística 2023b), representing roughly 17% of the country's population. The city of Porto is located on the northern coast of the country, facing the Atlantic Ocean and along the right bank of the River Douro. Its topography is hilly, with levels ranging from sea level to 200 metres high, encompassing steep slopes in some areas (Câmara do Porto, 2024a). There are currently 3 operational mechanised links between different elevations (The Guindais Funicular, the Lada Elevator and the Miragaia Mechanised Stairs) and 2 more are planned (Câmara do Porto, 2024b). The city has a light rail metro system, integrated with trains and buses, under a single ticketing system called 'Andante', that covers the metropolitan area. The metropolitan bus network has recently undergone a reorganisation and is now operating under the name UNIR. This network is complementary to the urban bus network that operates in the city of Porto and five other municipalities that are part of the central urban core of the metropolitan area (namely: Gondomar, Maia, Matosinhos, Valongo and Vila Nova de Gaia).

The city is a major hub for economic, educational and cultural activities in northern Portugal, with several "R&D centres and emerging business clusters in the IT and creative sectors, biotechnology and health and mechanical engineering" (URBACT III programme, 2018, p.34). It is also an important tourist destination, with a historical centre recognized as a World Heritage Site by UNESCO since 1996 and experiencing rapid tourism development, recording one of the best sector performances in Portugal and Europe. As a matter of fact, the World Travel Awards recognised Porto as the World's Leading City Destination in 2022 (World Travel Awards, n.d.) and was shortlisted in 2023 as a European Capital and Green Pioneer of Smart Tourism, with special mention to measures

related to mobility and carbon neutrality (European Commission 2023). It is noteworthy that the number of tourist guests in Porto reached a historic high of 3.7 million in 2019 (InvestPorto 2023).

For its residents, the city has created The Porto Card, which offers access to a range of experiences and services within the municipality through a single, free card. One notable benefit is the +perto service, which allows residents to use taxi transport between predefined points for just 1€, covering a distance of up to 2.5 km. This service complements existing public transport options such as metro, bus, and train, and is available from 6 AM to midnight with no limit on the number of trips. To use this service, residents can either book online, provided they have the digital version of the Porto Card, or call the designated phone number. Additionally, the card offers free use of the Funicular dos Guindais and reduced rates for senior citizens using taxis for health-related trips. Other mobility advantages include discounted taxi services, free funicular rides, and reduced rates for bicycle parking at the City Park. To obtain the Porto Card, residents need to create an account, fill out a form specifying their preferences, and then receive the card either at a municipal space or by mail. This initiative showcases how the city is committed to providing its citizens with good incentives to use collective transport alternatives to the private vehicle.

Porto is a city that is strongly committed to transitioning towards carbon neutrality. At the European level, it has been selected as part of the EU mission of 100 climate neutral and smart cities by 2030. It is also a member of the Transport Decarbonisation Alliance and of the Covenant of Mayors, both networks that strengthen the political momentum to drive sustainability transitions and promote transnational collaboration. At the local level, the municipality has recognised the strong role that the transport sector has to achieve its carbon neutrality goals, as it is responsible for 40% of the carbon emissions of the city.

3.2. Key urban mobility challenges of Porto

The municipality's efforts are focused on encouraging public transport and promoting more active mobility, with soft modes such as walking and cycling being prioritised. The Porto Municipal Master Plan, with a strategic territorial approach for the 2021-2030 period, is the main spatial planning document at the city level. This includes actions such as: (i) strengthening public transport with high-quality bus corridors; (ii) changing private parking policies in specific zones; (iii) introducing four pilot areas in the city where on-street parking will progressively be eliminated (with the exception of logistics loading and unloading points) and the public space will be requalified, called "Zones XXI"; (iv) defining the infrastructure and network for soft modes³; and (v) establishing pedestrian zones in the Historic Center of Porto (Porto 2021). While Porto's built environment and infrastructure may not explicitly discourage car use yet, there are many planned measures that will contribute to discourage private car use. The city's Sustainable Urban Logistics Plan (Câmara do Porto, 2024a) is another example of a planning document that recognises the importance of reducing the transport sector carbon emissions, acknowledging the negative impacts of congestion not only for logistic operators and economic activities, but also for air quality and noise contamination.

According to the 2021 census results (Instituto Nacional de Estatísticas (INE)), almost 80% of the resident employed population of the Porto Metropolitan Area use the private car for commuting trips, but, this value is lower than 20% for the residents in the Porto municipality, which makes Porto the municipality with the lowest percentage of private car use for commuting out of the 17 municipalities of the metropolitan area (Instituto Nacional de Estatística 2023a). This highlights the intermunicipal nature of the challenge that the municipality of Porto faces in its efforts to promote a more sustainable balance between different transport modes, aiming to increase public transport ridership and the reduction of private cars usage.

Similarly, the data from the primary statistical study on the topic of mobility patterns, the Inquerito à Mobilidade (IMob), also conducted by INE, shows a private-car-intense mobility pattern, with 69% of trips within the Porto Metropolitan Area being carried out by individual transport modes.

3 Soft modes are understood here as encompassing both cycling and walking, as well as other displacement modes that have a lower carbon footprint, such as electric bicycles and scooters. In this sense, it is a term slightly broader than active modes, as it encapsulates mobility alternatives that are not necessarily as demanding on personal energy for physical activity and that might involve some sort of small motor device.

The IMob survey collected comprehensive data on household characteristics, trip purposes, transport modes and travel distances, enabling a detailed evaluation of the urban mobility dynamics. According to the results of IMob, in the Metropolitan area of Porto, public transport use accounted for only 11.1% of all trips, while soft modes (walking or cycling) was the second main transport mode after the private car, totalling 18.9% of all journeys (with only 0.4% related to cycling). Whereas the Municipality of Porto has the highest proportion of journeys by soft modes, with over 30% completed by walking or cycling.

According to this study by INE, the three main reasons reported by respondents for using public transport were: “the fact of “not driving/not having individual transport” (52.6%), the “lack of alternative” (49.1%) and the “price/cost of public transport” (38.2%)” (Instituto Nacional de Estatística, 2018, p.80). The first reason supports the hypothesis that symbolic and affective motives are variables that might be at play for mode choice (Steg, 2005), alongside instrumental reasons such as travel time and level of service. Therefore, in order to reduce car dependency, it is paramount to seek a more systemic understanding of factors that influence mode choice and to what extent they do so (Beirão and Sasfield Cabral, 2007). This upholds the claim that knowledge from the Social Sciences and Humanities can bring valuable insights and methods for climate action in general and to sustainable mobility policy and measures.

In a recent study (Rocha et al., 2023) that focuses on factors influencing individual modal choices in the Porto Metropolitan Area, the authors identified a significant reliance on private motorised vehicles in the region, with a smaller proportion of the residents using active modes or public transport. They also explored the relationship between distance and modal choice, finding a preference for private motorised vehicles that increases with distance (Rocha et al., 2023). Their findings also call attention to the supramunicipal spatial nature of the mobility challenges authorities face in functional urban areas. As a result, one of their key recommendations is improving the public transport system, fostering intermodality and promoting a better coverage of the network.

It is important to highlight that multilevel and intermunicipal coordination for mobility policies is a key governance challenge to address. For example, addressing congestion on roads often exceeds the prerogatives of the municipality of Porto, as much of the traffic is on roads managed at the national level and often associated with commuting dynamics. The main example is the Via de Cintura Interna do Porto (VCI) road that presents a unique challenge due to the intersection of national and local interests. The VCI is managed at the national level, yet its congestion is primarily a local issue, impacting the daily lives of Porto’s residents and commuters. This multilevel nature of the problem complicates efforts to implement solutions like congestion pricing. While congestion pricing could potentially alleviate traffic jams and reduce environmental impact, its implementation requires coordination between national and local authorities. This example also support the importance of establishing coordination and participatory mechanisms that can enable policies that respond to the specific needs of a territory,

Another key recommendation is establishing an ongoing data collection practice to support informed decision making. The city of Porto (and the broader metropolitan area) could benefit from a more comprehensive and updated data set regarding transport and mobility. This would allow improved planning and implementation of more effective decarbonisation measures. For instance, there is little data about the role of tourism and tourists mobility patterns, but evidence points to considerable contributions of the sector to emissions in Porto (Russo et al., 2020). There is also little data regarding the impact of Covid-19 on mobility patterns and preferences, with the INE mobility survey of 2017 still posing as the main descriptive statistical reference for examining mobility.

A comprehensive and updated collection of datasets on transport and mobility, including the impacts of tourism and post Covid-19 mobility patterns, is essential for effective urban planning. These datasets should emphasise interoperability, openness, and connections with other topics such as air quality, public health, land use and urban form. It is important to gather not only quantitative data but also qualitative data such as from focus groups, interviews, surveys, and co-creation workshops. This approach would provide a more comprehensive view, delivering an integrated understanding of the issues. By incorporating Social Sciences and Humanities from the early stages of policy-making, it ensures these perspectives contribute meaningfully to the development process, rather than being added later solely to enhance communication and engagement. This holistic approach could support the development of policies that enhance public transport usage, reduce car dependency, and improve overall urban livability and air quality.

In conclusion, Porto's commitment to carbon neutrality and sustainable urban mobility is evident through strategic plans, policy measures and participation in European initiatives. The municipality recognises the crucial role of the transport sector in achieving carbon neutrality, however, challenges persist, particularly in addressing private-car-intensive mobility patterns.

3.3. The Porto workshop: Facilitating knowledge exchange to initiate a CoP

The knowledge brokerage workshop in Porto was a 2-day intense activity (17th and 18th of April 2024), marked by robust participation and dynamic interactions. Organised as part of the SSH CENTRE project, the workshop convened researchers and practitioners dedicated to advancing sustainable urban mobility transitions.

During the workshop's initial day, participants engaged in interactive sessions, including fishbowl discussions and a world café, that allowed for enriching exchanges of experiences. A city tour during the afternoon provided participants with first-hand insights into Porto's urban mobility landscape, offering glimpses into both its historical charm of the historical city centre and contemporary challenges. The experience of traffic congestion on a public bus underscored the real-world complexities of urban mobility—a valuable lesson in understanding the city's intricate dynamics.

The workshop's second day delved into the concept of CoPs as strategic collaboration mechanisms for advancing integrated and human-centred urban mobility policies. Discussions on establishing effective CoPs, including vision-building and stakeholder mapping, paved the way for engaging activities, including a role-playing game that promotes spatial awareness and empathy building. This immersive exercise facilitated reflections on transport justice and underscored the importance of broad engagement strategies in shaping inclusive urban mobility policies.

Prior to the workshop, a range of preliminary options had been crafted tailored to address the city of Porto identified challenges and needs. After the city selected a proposal aimed at fostering public transport and reducing private vehicle usage through a CoP, this concept was further developed from an interdisciplinary perspective.

The workshop provided a valuable opportunity to test key aspects of the proposal. It was observed that city officials and technicians from Porto and other cities (Schaerbeek, Belgium; Sofia, Bulgaria; Prague, Czech Republic; Suceava and Ramnicu Valcea, Romania; Beringen, Belgium; and Guimarães and Braga, Portugal) often understand the necessary actions to promote sustainable urban mobility from a normative perspective but struggle with implementation due to challenges in multilevel coordination and multistakeholder collaboration. Despite different local contexts, participants found that challenges are often very similar, indicating potential for policy transfer. Clear language with well-defined concepts emerged as crucial for bridging disciplines and overcoming institutional silos. Discussions highlighted the importance of narratives and framings in political issues, underscoring the role of social sciences and humanities in knowledge brokerage between researchers and practitioners.

The insights gained in the workshop helped to develop and inform the content of this document, using the European Commission Playbook of Communities of Practice as a central reference. Whilst this document is initially conceived to address key challenges of the Porto mobility system, an aim is to ensure that the roadmap is valuable to other cities as well. This roadmap is adaptable and beneficial for diverse urban contexts.

3.4. Data to support the establishment of the CoP

In general, during the Porto workshop, three major issues with obtaining (and using) data emerged from the discussion: 1) knowledge about what data exists, 2) data quality and trust issues and 3) knowledge about who owns the data and what users are permitted to do with it. Suggestions for municipal statistics that could be made available as open data included weather observations, road quality or air quality. Most participants had a low level of knowledge about available open data and many stated that an overview of available data was lacking. The city representatives mentioned using the *Strava app* to identify people's behaviour patterns and car registration statistics to collect data on car ownership. In this case, there have been attempts to set up a system to pull activity data based on dates. However, participants have encountered problems during the setup. The main issues mentioned include trouble getting the needed access codes, errors during the login process and difficulties accessing certain pieces of data. There were calls for better databases or other portals for open data, as well as intuitive and easy-to-use user interfaces for retrieving and submitting data. Current standards for open data dissemination and the technical platforms for offering this information openly were suggested to be less developed. Data quality was also questioned, exemplified by air quality monitoring. Improved data presentation and clarification, such as better feedback from data providers and the addition of metadata (e.g. population statistics), might help address these issues. Aggregating data (eg. clustering) could improve quality through the strength in numbers, though some participants preferred the ability to sort and evaluate each piece of information individually based on the context. Data ownership was another complex issue. Local cities had published data to fulfil specific legislation, while citizens attempted to gather and compile data to highlight deficiencies in data and pressure them to improve.

Data from the *Anda app* has the potential to be utilised for the establishment of the CoP. Porto developed the *Anda App*, allowing smartphone users to make payments using their mobile phones. Data from *Anda* could be instrumental in creating *personas*⁴ and to understand who is most likely to adopt mobile ticketing in their daily routine. This data can provide detailed insights into user behaviours, preferences and demographics, which are crucial for developing accurate and representative *personas*. Furthermore, this would enable addressing questions about peak travel times, revealing the busiest periods for specific *personas*. It could also help in understanding the travel patterns and purposes of non-frequent journeys.

Additional future work could concentrate on collecting and understanding data on people's mobility habits and decision-making processes. A smartphone-based GPS travel survey could be implemented, with participants providing details about their daily activities and travels over several days. The survey could also capture past experiences, travel habits and use of other modes of transport. The survey could be incorporated into the *Anda app* (Carrel, Sengupta and Walker, 2017). The findings of the survey could be complemented by in-depth qualitative research to explore, for example, how changes in the life course impact travel choices (e.g. the case of graduate employees) and family and friend influence on choosing different modes of travel.

Anda lacks essential features like route planning and real-time schedules, which are crucial for a comprehensive travel experience. Thus, it becomes feasible to gather pertinent data for temporal analysis, such as the time between scheduled and actual time of arrival (i.e. delays), the length of time spent picking up/dropping off passengers at bus stops and length of time to travel between the stops. The delay attribute is useful, for example, to assess the traffic congestion caused by roadwork. Patterns and trends in delay may emerge on a daily or weekly basis, helping the prediction of delays.

In summary, real-time data offers a modern approach to providing up-to-date information to passengers, improving their travel experiences. It facilitates the creation of new services (e.g. mobility as service) and has the potential to reduce traffic congestion and unnecessary environmental pollution.

⁴ Personas represent different types of residents or users of urban spaces. These personas help planners understand the diverse needs, behaviors, goals and challenges faced by various community members, allowing for more inclusive and effective urban development strategies. More on Personas in chapter 3.5.4.

3.5. Next steps for establishing a CoP for sustainable urban mobility for the City of Porto

Building on the guiding questions outlined in the CoP section (Section 2), this section offers a series of insights for establishing a Community of Practice in Porto. These recommendations are designed to help achieve the city's ambitious climate goals while also promoting inclusiveness and representativeness.

3.5.1. Why

As previously stated, Porto aims to be at the forefront of climate action in Portugal and across Europe. Through the Porto Climate Pact, the city has set a bold goal of reaching net-zero emissions by 2030. This goal supports the establishment of a CoP which connects people across the public and private sectors that tend to not communicate. Indeed, it appears that the current authorities have not found a channel to efficiently communicate the planned changes in urban mobility to their citizens or to the other stakeholders from the private and public sectors. This gap can be addressed by the creation of a CoP to enable a systemic way to generate good mobility practices, collectively discuss mobility-related issues, and produce information and accessible knowledge to be used in the sustainable transition.

The transition towards sustainable mobility should be intended as a social process involving a large number of stakeholders with different interests and individual needs. In addition to engaging various actors, achieving climate neutrality impacts numerous sectors, including energy, public health and logistics. People involved need to feel closer to the political decision over urban mobility as well as be actively part of the process. For these reasons, the CoP can promote an environment of sharing knowledge, collective learning, building of relationships and a sense of belonging and mutual commitment to promoting sustainable mobility and climate change objectives.

Establishing a CoP can help to promote long-term sustainability strategies and actions, instead of short-term solutions that are usually taken to solve imminent problems related to the mobility of the city. This can result in a more cohesive strategy among different stakeholders, reducing the gap between technical and political expertise, including citizens' needs. The complex path that is behind the creation of a mobility CoP is outlined in the graphical recording of the workshop by Luisa G. Costa.

Figure 4. Infographic on the creation of the CoP created during the workshop in Porto, April 2024.

3.5.2. What

The primary objective of the CoP initiative in Porto is to establish a peer-to-peer network of advocates dedicated to advancing sustainable mobility and climate change objectives. Unlike traditional CoPs, which often focus solely on technical expertise, Porto's initiative could benefit from placing a strong emphasis on interdisciplinarity. Central to this approach is the recognition that sustainable mobility is not only about reducing carbon emissions but also about promoting equity and accessibility, particularly for marginalised communities. A main purpose of this network can be to promote the need for behavioural change related to mobility. This could be facilitated by dissemination events and assemblies aimed at raising the awareness and interests of a large number of people.

At the core of Porto's CoP initiative is the promotion of public transport and equitable mobility. Prioritising fairness and inclusivity, Porto seeks to address not only environmental concerns but also social and economic inequalities, for a better understanding of mobility needs and barriers of different groups of stakeholders. By addressing these broader societal challenges at two main levels, municipal and collective, Porto's CoP initiative could strive to create a more just and sustainable urban environment for the entire community.

3.5.3. Who

This holistic approach needs to first identify target groups of stakeholders, identify specific needs and create a stakeholder map able to clarify their potential role in contributing to the CoP on mobility. In addition to engaging stakeholders directly involved in mobility initiatives, achieving climate neutrality also necessitates collaboration across various sectors, including energy, public health, land use, telecommunication and information technology, among others. The interconnectedness of these sectors underscores the complexity of the challenge and emphasises the importance of fostering collaboration and knowledge-sharing among stakeholders.

The stakeholder map defined at the workshop provides a starting foundation. For instance, an Influence-Interest Matrix was created where the participants identified and placed stakeholders on the matrix Figure.

Figure 5. Infographic on stakeholder mapping

It is of note that the majority of the stakeholders are in the upper left quadrant, meaning that they are usually excluded from decision making and are taken into account less. The construction of a CoP in Porto, through the different levels of participation mentioned in Section 2.3, will facilitate those groups of stakeholders to take action and empower themselves.

3.5.4. How

It is necessary to engage with organisations and individuals from the City of Porto to introduce the concept of CoP, answer questions and identify potential members to participate. Several engagement strategies exist. For example, in the Porto workshop, stakeholder's needs were explored through participation in serious games aimed at discovering their needs and expectations regarding urban mobility. These approaches can then be replicated and adapted by the participants in their own contexts.

In particular, storytelling can prove advantageous in tackling intricate and 'wicked' challenges, such as transitioning towards sustainability in mobility. Storytelling fosters an environment conducive to acknowledging and learning from varied viewpoints, facilitated by stakeholders and citizens from diverse backgrounds and perspectives. Usually, the starting point is a collaborative story with common ground to acknowledge where the differences lie. They are asked to articulate their opinion and describe their experiences, but afterwards, they are also encouraged to be creative. Without necessarily leading to a consensus, storytelling promotes mutual understanding and collective action. With a specific focus on the CoPs, storytelling could help in creating collaboration across disciplines and sectors. This may increase the complexity but also helps in solving conflicts derived from contrasting opinions.

Storytelling can encounter some challenges. It requires a wide range of expertise beyond mere stories, and includes the need for skills in organisation, facilitation and analytical assessment. The outcomes from storytelling should be translated into practical efforts, to provide value to the stakeholder contribution. Other problems can include conflicting norms, values and perspectives. Moreover, the high economic cost and the interconnections with other problems complicate finding a common solution.

While storytelling is easier to adapt to different contexts, in the workshop a serious game was played that was relevant to mobility related behavioural change and engaging with different profiles of users, named "Hands on map". This game drives a reflection on the barriers and limits of users that do not allow them to have or prefer sustainable mobility choices. It stimulates design thinking through the promotion of a number of *personas* and real maps. After the final brainstorming, the participants can shift from the simulation to real-life mobility problems.

In general, serious gaming is grounded in play and gaming principles that prioritise learning for change, rather than mere entertainment. Indeed, they are engagement activities that can raise the awareness and understanding of complex issues, such as urban mobility problems. These games are tailored to educate individuals on intricate and systemic issues, such as climate change and mobility. They span a wide array of formats, including computer games, board games, card games, role-playing scenarios, virtual reality simulations and other interactive learning mediums integrating game elements (SSH Open Knowledge Platform).

They are characterised by different phases which correspond to the following:

- Plan: organising the context in which participants will play;
- Recruit participants: identify who will be the participants to shape the rules and explanation based on their characteristics (i.e. adults, pupils, policy-makers);
- Introduce the game and rules: it is fundamental to clearly explain the game, provide a description of the story behind the game and clarify the rules, addressing any potential misunderstanding;
- Play: the time dedicated to the active phase of playing is often facilitated by an expert, ready to solve problems conflicts and answer to questions from the participants;

- **Reflect:** this phase regards the discussion on the playing experience, where participants can give feedback and reflections on the play activities but also they try to identify some conclusions that can be transferred to the real world.

Serious games are often useful in promoting collaboration and strategic thinking among participants, but also they can contribute learning enhancement through the experiences. These experiences enable different groups of people to access complex problems, usually limited to a restricted group of experts. This generates new insight into problems and enhances participants' problem solving skills.

Besides the positive aspects of using serious games, challenges and limitations exist and need to be considered. It is common to face a lack of knowledge transfer from the game to real life, which is also often accompanied by over-simplifications of complex topics to make them easily understandable. Furthermore, designing serious games is not an easy task and often requires the professional input of game designers. Jessen et al. (2018) highlights the involvement of co-designers to increase player experiences by emphasising how game visuals, competitions and interactions can motivate player engagement with the game and its objectives. Additionally, co-designers actively participate in discussions on prototype game mechanisms and rules, aiming to make the game more realistic and unbiased and potentially revealing various institutional responses. Moreover, serious games represent a direct interaction between stakeholders and academic research outcomes, functioning as a mediating layer for the practical application of knowledge.

As already mentioned, there are several serious games useful in engagement strategies, some of them use *personas* instead of real people that can somehow substitute individuals. Vallet et al., (2020) highlight a paradigm shift in mobility behaviour analysis, introducing the Scenario Persona narrative method, combining scenario thinking and *personas* for generating detailed individualised narratives. This method, demonstrated in a case study on urban mobility, involves experts creating *personas* and narratives across scenarios, offering a tangible understanding of potential effects on diverse social groups.

The development of *personas* is based on research, on what is possible to learn from people and bring it into the design process. For serious games in the context of mobility, a user *persona* is a representation of the goals and travel behaviours of a group of users, or represents different profiles of users based on socio-demographic characteristics. It needs to be attached to a specific context and be developed based on empirical user research.

Sometimes, *personas* are synthesised from data collected from interviews with users because otherwise *personas* will be based on biases and personal perception of the reality. Cherry et al., (2022) acknowledge the need for careful facilitation to prevent cultural stereotyping in this method.

Indeed, *personas* are crucial to give emphasis to those groups often excluded to be engaged, for example, older people, children, women and people with disabilities. Their interests should be balanced with the other individuals' interests but it should also receive more attention to deconstruct social, informational and infrastructural barriers.

At an engagement level, the use of *personas* in developing CoP can be a tool to enrich collaboration and cooperation on common practices and aims, while otherwise each individual could be concentrated or influenced by his/her self interests, but they do not substitute people in reality. The coordination between members of a CoP can work if there is an agreement on common objectives.

3.5.5. From strategies to action plan

A detailed list of opportunities and challenges to be addressed are derived from the previous steps. They can assist in commencing the discussion and choosing the best mobility measures to be implemented while searching for a consensus among the stakeholders. As noted during the workshop, it is fundamental to find a broad consensus, instead of an agreement of the majority.

These steps can be translated into a preliminary action plan to better denote the common vision and the first proceedings to realise the purpose of a CoP. To do so, stronger connections and collaboration with universities and other partners are required, as well as a clear data collection method that could support the policymaking process.

Furthermore, to operate, the CoP often needs some funding. The type of funding depends on the diverse formats of the CoP, as outlined in the following list of potential funding sources:

- Interreg - a European Commission's programme supporting cooperation in four thematic priorities dealing with territorial cohesion and eight specific objectives, based on the outcomes of the territorial analysis. Source: <https://interreg.eu/programme/interreg-atlantic-area/>, <https://interreg.eu/programme/interreg-spain-portugal-poctep/>.
- Driving Urban Transitions to a Sustainable Future - a partnership aimed at tackling urban challenges, by supporting local authorities and municipalities, service and infrastructure providers, and citizens in capacity building, research and innovation to translate global strategies into local action. Source: <https://dutpartnership.eu/>.
- COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology) - a funding organisation for research and innovation networks, connecting research initiatives across Europe and innovators to grow their ideas by sharing them with their peers. COST Actions are bottom-up networks with a duration of four years that boost research, innovation and careers. Source: <https://www.cost.eu/>.
- European Urban Initiative - a fund providing real opportunities for cities to reach sustainable development at different stages, but also to take the risk of innovation and to turn ideas into pilot projects for the urban environment. Source: <https://www.urban-initiative.eu/about-innovative-actions>.
- Recovery and Resilience National Plan - a national instrument for EU members to bring grants and loans to support reforms and investments for making greener and digital transitions in several fields.
- Horizon Europe - particularly calls related to the City-Missions, such as Changing urban spaces and mindsets to accelerate the transition to climate neutrality (HORIZON-MISS-2024-CIT-01). Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-miss-2024-cit-01-01?order=DESC&pageNumber=1&pageSize=50&sortBy=relevance&keywords=urban&isExactMatch=true&status=31094501,31094502&framework-Programme=43108390>

These opportunities can increase the feasibility of the CoP and its long-term operation.

4. Conclusions and next steps

In the section dedicated to Communities of Practice (CoP) (Section 2), there was an exploration of the strategic role they can have in facilitating knowledge exchange, collaborative learning, and problem-solving within the realm of sustainable urban mobility transitions. The investigation into the conceptual landscape of CoPs, alongside findings and insights from exchanges and workshops, shed light on their significance, operational aspects, and diverse applications. Through real-world exploration of the Porto case study, a roadmap has been developed that can be used as inspiration for next steps, transforming the lessons from the knowledge brokerage initiative into an operational CoP.

In the section dedicated to the preliminary Roadmap for CoPs in Porto's mobility initiatives (section 3), the key steps and recommendations towards effectively establishing a CoP that can help to achieve the city's ambitious climate goals whilst also promoting inclusiveness and representativeness are highlighted.

It is important to stress that Porto's CoP is well advised to embrace the interconnectedness of mobility with other sectors, such as energy and public health as well the need for collaboration across diverse stakeholder groups.

Moving forward, Porto's CoP initiative could focus on some key aspects to ensure its success:

1. **Stakeholder mapping and engagement:** Although a preliminary mapping exercise was conducted during the workshop and can serve as a basis it would be important to conduct a more robust mapping. This exercise could be done remotely, but it would be advisable to engage the key players that have already been identified. Continuous engagement with stakeholders from various sectors such as construction, energy and public health can broaden participation and foster collaboration. Moreover, strengthening collaboration with the academic community, who can provide valuable knowledge and expertise on achieving key targets such as mobility net-zero and socio-spatial integration, are instrumental. Academic research and insights, can inform evidence-based decision-making and develop innovative solutions to advance mobility initiatives forward. Community engagement and education, including public awareness campaigns and public participation in pilot projects, are vital for fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility.
2. **Capacity building and networking:** Provide training and resources to stakeholders (including STCP and Metro do Porto) to enhance their understanding of sustainable mobility and climate change objectives. Furthermore, continuing to share experiences and best practices from other European cities will provide valuable insights and inspiration for our own initiatives.
3. **Policy advocacy:** Advocate for policy changes and initiatives that support sustainable mobility and climate neutrality goals at the local, national and European levels. Positioning Porto as a leader in advocating for sustainable mobility policies strengthened its reputation as a forward-thinking city committed to environmental stewardship. This reputation can attract investment, businesses and talent drawn to the city's sustainability initiatives, thereby fostering economic growth and development. During the Pope's visit, STPC was asked to increase the number of buses on specific routes. Similarly, during the "Queima das Fitas" academic societies promoted public transport, leading to over 700 additional bus trips. These initiatives align with Porto's ambitious goal of achieving net-zero emissions, demonstrating a commitment to sustainable urban mobility and reducing the city's carbon footprint.
4. **Implementation:** Work collaboratively to implement concrete actions and projects that advance sustainable mobility objectives and contribute to Porto's net-zero emissions target by 2030. In the case of Porto, a collaborative effort is essential to implement tangible actions and projects aimed at advancing sustainable mobility and contributing to the city's goal of achieving net-zero emissions by 2030. Key strategies include the development and promotion of the Porto and Andante Travel Card schemes, which should integrate seamlessly with all modes of public transportation, offer incentives for frequent use and should be made convenient using physical and digital transport platforms. Expanding and modernising the public transport network, transitioning to

green fleets and ensuring accessibility are crucial. Promoting active transport through dedicated bike lanes, pedestrian pathways and expanded bike-sharing programs will further encourage sustainable mobility. Implementing smart mobility solutions, such as real-time information systems and a Mobility-as-a-Service platform, can enhance user experience and efficiency.

5. Monitoring and evaluation: Establish mechanisms for monitoring progress and evaluating the effectiveness of CoP initiatives, allowing for iterative improvements and adjustments as needed.

Firstly, develop a robust framework for performance metrics and indicators. This should include SMART metrics related to sustainable mobility, such as reductions in greenhouse gas emissions, increases in public transport usage, decreases in private vehicle use and improvements in air quality. During the workshop, a road safety indicator was presented, measured by the number of accidents, accident severity, road hierarchy and citizen science. Similar indicators should be developed for sustainable mobility.

For example, metrics could include:

- Greenhouse gas emissions to measure reductions in emissions from transport sources;
- Public transportation usage to track increases in the number of public transport users and frequency of use.
- Private vehicle use to monitor decreases in the number of private vehicles on the road.
- Air quality assessments to monitor air pollution levels.

Furthermore, the potential of implementing a comprehensive data collection and management system should be explored. This could include utilising advanced technologies such as Internet of Things sensors, GPS tracking and big data analytics to gather real-time data on transport patterns, vehicle emissions and public transport efficiency. This data should be accessible and transparent to all stakeholders involved. During the workshop, it was mentioned that real-time data already exists; however, it is crucial to ensure that this data is also shared with academic researchers who can develop innovative solutions. A solution could be to establish a centralised data platform where all collected data can be stored, processed and analysed. This platform should include features for secure data sharing, user-friendly interfaces for different stakeholder groups and tools for visualising data trends and insights. Additionally, there is a need for creation of protocols and agreements for data sharing that protect privacy and intellectual property while enabling academic researchers and other partners to access the data they need for analysis and innovation.

In addition, there should be the establishment of a centralised monitoring body or committee responsible for overseeing the progress of CoP initiatives. This body should include representatives from local government, public transportation agencies, environmental organisations and community groups. Their role will be to review data, assess performance against the established metrics and provide regular reports to all stakeholders.

There should be the creation of feedback loops and participatory mechanisms. This includes engaging with the community and stakeholders through surveys, public forums and feedback sessions to gather insights and suggestions on the implemented initiatives. This participatory approach ensures that the initiatives remain relevant and aligned with the needs and expectations of the community.

In conclusion, establishing a CoP for sustainable urban mobility in Porto presents an invaluable opportunity to better understand the motivations, needs, and aspirations of both citizens and key mobility stakeholders. This collaborative framework will be instrumental in fostering increased public transport uptake while minimising the reliance on private cars. By doing so, Porto can make significant strides toward the decarbonisation of its transport sector and contribute to its ambitious climate goals. Additionally, the CoP can play a crucial role in enhancing the overall quality of life and accessibility for all residents, ensuring that sustainable mobility solutions are not only environmentally beneficial but also socially inclusive and responsive to the community's needs.

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